

VIDEO TUTORIALS AND BAKING PERFORMANCE AMONG GRADE 10 STUDENTS

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Video Tutorials and Baking Performance among Grade 10 Students

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Abstract

This study focused on the perception of the students on the video tutorials as a learning tool used in teaching Bread and Pastry production and its relationship with their baking performance. The descriptive-correlational research approach has been employed that uses video tutorials and survey questionnaires. The respondents are Grade 10 students in San Antonio National High School at San Antonio, Quezon during the school year 2023-2024. In identifying the respondents of the study, total enumeration of the population was considered, thus, no sampling technique was applied. The respondents generally perceived the video tutorials positively with favorable responses on objectives, content, instructions, audio and visual quality, and frequency of use. Similarly, their baking performances received positive feedback, particularly in presentation, taste and texture, time management, and food safety and hygiene. The study found out that the video tutorials in terms of its components such as objective, content, and instructions do not significantly related to students baking technical skills performance. Moreover, in significant relationship also exerted between students' baking performance and the video tutorial audio quality, visual quality and frequency of use. On the other hand, the students' average baking performance was associated with video tutorials visual quality and frequency of use.

Keywords: *average baking performance, baking performance, bread and pastry production, technical skills*

Introduction

Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) holds a significant role within our current educational system, particularly in equipping individuals with practical skills that can be applied for their sustenance and survival. The curriculum of this subject encompasses various essential life skills that will equip students with the necessary tools to thrive autonomously in their chosen career paths. The primary significance of Technology and Livelihood Education lies in its ability to impart knowledge that is not only relevant to students' current lives but also remains consistently applicable as they progress in their educational journey. Additionally, individuals are anticipated to cultivate and strengthen their entrepreneurial mindset, with the ultimate goal of establishing their own enterprise in the foreseeable future.

The Bread and Pastry Production is a course offered under Technology and Livelihood Education, It is designed for high school student to develop knowledge, skills, and attitude to perform the tasks. It covers core competencies namely: 1) prepare and produce bakery products; 2) prepare and produce pastry products; 3) prepare and present gâteau, tortes, and cakes; 4) prepare and display petit fours and 5) present desserts.

Numerous young people appreciate baking. For many individuals, engaging in this activity serves as a recreational pursuit, a means of alleviating stress, and occasionally a means of generating income. Online video tutorials on baking can be a valuable resource for individual seeking to acquire baking skills. The act of observing video clips facilitates the rapid identification of areas requiring improvement and the prevention of errors, thereby promoting the organization of one's output. Video clips are a valuable resource for teachers, as they provide significant assistance in the preparation of baking activities. This instructional method facilitates rapid comprehension of the correct procedures by learners, enabling them to promptly seek clarification on any unaddressed queries arising from the video content.

Baking is an activity that adheres to numerous distinct standards. Similar to scientific practices, the art of pastry requires a remarkable degree of precision and accuracy. A slight change in variables such as temperature, time of day, or humidity can greatly influence the ultimate result. In the realm of cookery, it is imperative to minimize the occurrence of unexpected outcomes.

Prior to commencing the baking process, it is imperative for children to acquire a comprehensive understanding of the various tools and equipment involved. Additionally, they should possess the knowledge of accurately weighing and converting the components required for the recipe. Lastly, it is crucial for children to prioritize their safety by wearing appropriate personal protective equipment. The individual should possess the ability to understand and interpret a blueprint. In order to ensure successful outcomes in their culinary profession, individuals must possess a comprehensive understanding of the various components comprising a formula.

The primary challenge typically lies in the ability to consistently recall the importance of reviewing the instructions prior to commencing. Before beginning the task it is advisable to thoroughly review the instructions and then create a visual list of all the required materials.

Not all online videos possess the suitability for instructing baking techniques. A comprehensive examination of the video content to be utilized in each lesson is necessary.

The utilization of video tutorials has the potential to enhance students' creativity and motivation. The purpose of these videos is to assist teachers in effectively engaging and educating their students. This phenomenon has a significant impact on the methods and levels of student engagement and study practice utilizations in the present day. Video lessons, when utilized alongside modular lessons, have been reported to enhance students' comprehension of the taught concepts. According to Insorio and Macandog (2022), the application of YouTube videos by students was highly appreciated due to the valuable opportunity it provided to observe their teachers delivering demonstrations on a wide range of subjects. Students commonly submit a formal request to their instructor, seeking access to films that offer supplementary examples and explanations delivered in a distinct and pronounced accent.

In a study conducted by Ebied, Kahouf, and Abdel Rahman (2016), it was determined that YouTube plays a significant role in the field of computer education. The study conducted revealed that YouTube lessons have proven to be effective in acquiring fundamental and digital skills. The material is utilized and integrated into an audiovisual application that showcases the application of skills and visual representations, enhancing the understanding of the subject matter.

In Bread and Pastry, the students are being provided with the necessary knowledge and skills to ensure a prosperous future. Additionally, it serves as an introduction to the concepts of business and entrepreneurship. Teachers are enhancing their teaching materials by incorporating strategies for managing a business or small enterprise. The students are acquiring knowledge and skills in entrepreneurship, as well as gaining a comprehensive understanding of the business industry. The students have the potential to become future proprietors of thriving food chains, grocery stores, bakeries, and other prominent establishments. Additionally, it is guiding the students towards future employment opportunities.

The Curriculum Guide remains the same for the majority of the TLE (Technology and Livelihood Education) and TVL (Technical-Vocational-Livelihood) specializations. The reason why MELC (Most Essential Learning Competencies) were not recognized is because they are aligned with the Training Regulations (TR) of TESDA, which have not been revised to accommodate the current situation. However, these competencies will still be taught using flexible learning methods, as outlined in TESDA Circular No. 62, s. 2020.

In order to optimize the educational experience for students, it is essential to provide them with tools that facilitate information absorption and self-monitoring of their comprehension. In order to optimize the utilization of our educational videos, it is imperative to provide students with guidance in the areas of processing and self-evaluation, which are essential for achieving the intended learning outcomes.

The objective of this research paper is to investigate the educational efficacy of video tutorials on Bread and Pastry Production topics and consolidate the videos into a single file that can be easily accessed by TLE teachers. The purpose of this study was to use ready-made instructional baking videos that would assist Grade 10 students.

The students presented with a variety of video learning activity clips corresponding to the specific topic or skill they need to practice. These tools can serve as effective motivators for students, offering a diverse range of instructional activities that cater to different ability levels and learning styles. Students may be required to engage in either independent or collaborative work.

Methodology

Research Design

This study applied descriptive-correlational type of research. This research identified the profile of the students as well as their family's occupation and monthly income. This study also sought for the development on new possibilities and learning opportunities with the use of video tutorials in developing baking skills of the students and enhance their baking performance.

To explain this briefly, the goal of this study was to describe perception of respondents on the components, characteristics and frequency of use of the video tutorials and level of baking performance of the students with the use of video tutorials together with their average baking performance.

Respondents

The respondents of this study was composed of seventy-eight (78) Grade 10 TLE students belonging to two (2) classes of San Antonio National High School San Antonio, Quezon for the school year 2023-2024. There are forty-four (44) male and thirty-four (34) female. They lived mostly in remote areas but different internet access.

Table 1. *Distribution of Students*

Grade Level	Section	No. of Respondents
10	Apolinario Mabini	39
10	Gabriela Silang	39
Total		78

In identifying the respondents of the study, the total enumeration of the population was considered; thus, no sampling technique was applied since the total enrollees of the two sections were considered the subjects of the study. These two (2) sections were handled by

the teacher.

Instruments

The researcher gathered the important data through the use of a survey questionnaire that the students answered. The non-standardized questionnaire used by the researcher was composed of two parts: Part I is for the profile of the students in terms of age, gender, family background (income and parent's educational attainment); Part II consists of the perception of the respondents on video tutorials as learning tool in terms of component and characteristic that consist of 5 item indicators each variable and frequency of use. Lastly, the performance rubrics with numerical rating.

The instrument was validated by five (5) TLE teachers from San Antonio National High School including our Department head, two Teacher III, one Teacher II and one Teacher I. The copies of the research instrument and letter seeking for their time to validate the said instrument.

Procedure

A letter of approval to conduct the study and copies of research instrument was sent to the office of our division Deped Quezon, then after the approval a copy was also given to the district office as well as to our school principal to official start the study.

The researcher develop video tutorials in baking cakes. She considered the components and characteristics of a video tutorials, later it was uploaded to her youtube account. Due to some internet connectivity issues some videos were copied and downloaded on their mobile phones. Each video tutorials was based on the performance task to be made in Bread and Pastry Production. The video tutorial were presented to the experts in baking and expert in ICT to refine the video contents. The teacher assessed the students baked output and gave feedback thru the use of baking performance rubrics with numerical rating.

In the data collection, the students answered parts I and II after the lesson to determine their perception on the video tutorials and the students' level of baking performance if it helped in their learning and enriched their baking skills. While the rubrics has been used to rate their baking performance and output. The data on the performance of the students were recorded and encoded for statistical interpretation.

The data was sent initially to my statistician and got the approval to forward to our statistic center's email. After a week the interpreted data was sent back but with some missing data for interpretation. The data needed has been discussed altogether with my statistician, adviser and the statistic center head then finalized and was able to start the interpretation of data.

Results and Discussion

Part I. Profile of the Respondents

This part presents data on the frequency and percentage distribution of the profile of the respondents of TLE Grade 10 Students of San Antonio National High School. This includes age, sex, parent's occupation and family income.

Table 2. Summary of the Profile of Respondents

		Frequency	Percentage		
Age	15.00	35	44.9		
	16.00	38	48.7		
	17.00	2	2.6		
	18.00	1	1.3		
	19.00	2	2.6		
Gender	Female	34	43.6		
	Male	44	56.4		
				Father	Mother
Parents Educational Attainment	Elementary Undergraduate	13	16.7	7	9.0
	Elementary Graduate	25	32.1	18	23.1
	Secondary Undergraduate	14	17.9	12	15.4
	Secondary Graduate	23	29.5	32	41.0
	Vocational	-	-	1	1.3
	College Undergraduate	-	-	4	5.1
	College Graduate	3	3.8	4	5.1
Family monthly income	Below 10,000	48	61.5		
	10,001 -20,000	20	25.6		
	20,001 -30,000	9	11.5		
	30,001 -50,000	1	1.3		
	50,001 -Above	-	-		
Internet connectivity	Fiber	8	10.3		
	Limited Prepaid WiFi	25	32.1		
	Mobile Data	45	57.7		

Table 2 shows that the majority of the two classes of Grade 10 students at San Antonio National High School for the school year 2023-2024 are 16 years old (48.7 percent), followed by 15 years old (44.9 percent), 2.6 percent at the ages of 17 and 19, and 1.3 percent at the age of 18. This statistic shows that the majority of Grade 10 students are between the ages of 15 and 16.

In terms of gender it showed that males from the two classes of Grade 10 students at San Antonio National High School outweigh female students. The total number of responses is 78, with 34 (43.6 percent) female and 44 (56.4 percent) male. This result suggests that the majority of responses are male.

With regards to the parents educational attainment revealed that the majority of the respondent's father education was elementary graduate, consisting of 25 or 32.1 percent, followed by 23 or 29.5 percent with secondary graduate, 14 or 17.9 percent with secondary undergraduate, 13 or 16.7 percent with elementary undergraduate, and finally 3 or 3.8 percent with college graduate. It demonstrates that the majority of Grade 10 have fathers who have received primary education. It also revealed that the majority of the respondent's education of their mother was secondary graduate, with 32 or 41 percent, followed by 18 or 23.1 percent in elementary graduate, 12 or 15.4 percent secondary graduate, 7 or 9 percent elementary undergraduate, 4 or 5.1 percent for both college undergraduate and graduate, and 1 or 1.3% in vocational education. It reveals that the majority of Grade 10 student mothers have a secondary education. The majority of the respondent's parents had a secondary education.

In terms of family monthly income it shows that the majority of respondents have a house-hold income of 10,000 or less, with a 48 or 61.5 percent, followed by 10,001 to 20,000 with a 20 or 25.6 percent, then 20,001 to 30,000 with a 9 or 11.5 percent, and finally 30,001 to 50,000 with 1 or 1.3 percent. It demonstrates that the average household income of the student responders was less than 10,000.

Lastly from the internet connectivity reveals that the majority of respondents had mobile data (45 or 57.7 percent), followed by limited prepaid wifi (25 or 32.1%) and fiber connection (8 or 10.3 percent). It suggests that the majority of student respondents were connected using mobile data. This coincides to the fact that the parents monthly income are below minimum wage and prioritize their primary needs.

Part II – Perception Of Video Tutorials As Learning Tool

This part shows data on frequency and percentage of the Grade 10 TLE Student's – Respondent's based on video tutorials in terms of Components, Characteristic and Frequency of Use.

Table 3
Respondents' Perception on the Components of Video Tutorials in Teaching Bread and Pastry Production in terms of Objectives

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
<i>In video tutorials the objectives...</i>			
1. Provide a measurable and observable situation that match with the Training Regulations of TESDA	4.15	0.74	Manifested
2. Show the clear purpose of the lesson	4.40	0.84	Manifested
3. Describe how well the students will do.	4.53	0.66	Highly Manifested
4. Are achievable and include clear, transferable learning goals that give students greater control.	4.26	0.87	Manifested
5. Can suggest the outcomes in the affective, psychomotor, and cognitive domain	3.94	0.81	Manifested
Overall	4.25	0.55	Manifested

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Manifested; 3.50-4.49 Manifested; 2.50-3.49 Moderately Manifested; 1.50-2.49 Fairly Manifested; 1.00-1.49 Not Manifested

As shown on Table 3, the result indicate that the objectives in components of video tutorials were manifested among the students of Grade 10. As shown, most of the items obtained the verbal interpretation of manifested with the overall mean of 4.25 which signifies that they were listed in ways that conform to the guidelines. In addition to this, item 3 “the objectives describe how well the students will do” obtained the highest mean of 4.53 with verbal interpretation of highly manifested and item 5 “can suggest the outcomes in the affective, psychomotor, and cognitive domain obtained the lowest mean of 3.94 with verbal interpretation of manifested.

The learning materials should meet the standards of the curriculum and learning styles of the learners. The objectives of the lesson to be achieved after watching, was indicated and explained by the teacher before the actual performance task. The students has the interest and understanding on what are expected of them. It is important that clear instruction and achievable competencies has been considered. Therefore, the objectives of the lesson and three domains of learning was clearly stated and in the video tutorials provided.

According to Galatsopoulou et al. (2022), findings of there study have consequences for the design and development of educational

approaches and curriculum. Students with digital and media literacy require sophisticated methods of instruction and anticipate innovation and creativity to meet their learning styles and engage them in learning.

Table 4
Respondents' Perception on the Components of Video Tutorials in Teaching Bread and / Pastry Production in terms of Content

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
<i>In video tutorials the content...</i>			
1. is closely related to the objective and gives useful information.	4.55	0.68	Highly Manifested
2. has the right length and is suitable for the Students	4.46	0.66	Manifested
3. features effective and helpful conversation to respond and/or fulfill teachers' tasks.	4.51	0.68	Highly Manifested
4. organization and language used are both the transparent and precise.	4.17	0.83	Manifested
5. is accurate, complete, and adequate for each covered subject	4.38	0.83	Manifested
Overall	4.42	0.50	Manifested
<small>Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Manifested; 3.50-4.49 Manifested; 2.50-3.49 Moderately Manifested; 1.50-2.49 Fairly Manifested; 1.00-1.49 Not Manifested</small>			

Table 4 reveals that the content were manifested with the overall mean of 4.42. The content that is closely related to the objective and gives useful information and the features effective and helpful conversation to respond and/ or fulfill teacher's tasks obtained the highest mean of 4.55 and 4.51 respectively with the verbal interpretation highly manifested. While the indicator organization and language used are both transparent and precise obtained the lowest mean of 4.17 with the verbal interpretation manifested.

The data implicates that objectives has a big impact in gaining the information and skills expected to them. It should be simple and organize in the student's perspective to be able to achieve a favorable result. Only those important points to remember should be emphasized and the language or terms used are familiar to them prior to the performance. Furthermore, Khan et al. (2017) discovered that some of the best strategies for content delivery included providing different methods to acquire the content, defining expectations, breaking information down into smaller chunks, and making good use of the conversation. With the advancement of technology, the possibilities for information transmission and creation are limitless. Hence, the content of the video tutorials was effective for both teachers and learners. The contents should help and give complete information to guide the learners on their task.

Table 5
Respondents' Perception on the Components of Video Tutorials in Teaching Bread and Pastry Production in terms of Instruction

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
<i>In video tutorials the instructions...</i>			
1. Are easy to understand	4.51	0.72	Highly Manifested
2. Are all related to the subject and can improve critical thinking.	4.38	0.65	Manifested
3. Generate data related to the subject's desired learning outcome.	4.28	0.85	Manifested
4. Are relevant to the learning that is being evaluated.	4.29	0.81	Manifested
5. The exercises are interesting, exciting, and can improve students' learning skills.	4.45	0.91	Manifested
Overall	4.38	0.55	Manifested
<small>Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Manifested; 3.50-4.49 Manifested; 2.50-3.49 Moderately Manifested; 1.50-2.49 Fairly Manifested; 1.00-1.49 Not Manifested</small>			

Table 5 shows the result of the perception of the respondents on the instruction on video tutorial. The indicator 1 suggest that the instruction are easy to understand obtained the highest mean of 4.51 with the verbal interpretation of highly manifested. Furthermore, indicator 5 reflects that the exercises are interesting, exciting, and can improve students' learning skills obtained 4.45 mean with the

verbal interpretation manifested. On the other hand indicator 3 generate data related to the subject’s desired learning outcome obtained the lowest mean of 4.28 with the verbal interpretation of manifested.

A complete and detailed instruction is important in following a cooking or baking tutorial hence, it should be easy to follow and fun to make. The procedure should provide very simple and direct instructions throughout the tutorials. Making things easy can add more interest to the students to finish the video tutorials and focus to do the best to improve and gain knowledge and skills from the task. The same with the ingredients to be used it should be easy to find in the market or within the area, they are more excited in completing the ingredients and be prepared.

The work of Gelera et al. (2023), a mobile application for cooking tutorials, was created to preserve Filipino historical cuisines. The application was useful and effective for people who wanted to learn how to cook native dishes because it provided instructions on how to properly prepare traditional dishes using actual cooking time and a voice guide. Users enjoyed the app since it explained the step-by-step procedure of creating Filipino traditional meals. Therefore, the instructions on the video tutorials should be simple and easy to follow as well as the ingredients and tools to be used.

Table 6
Respondents’ Perception on the Characteristics of Video Tutorials in Teaching Bread and Pastry Production in terms of Audio quality

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
<i>In video tutorials the audio quality...</i>			
1. Is maintained at an appropriate pace and volume.	4.13	0.71	Manifested
2. Is clear and matches the order of the topics and learnings.	4.58	0.61	Highly Manifested
3. The sound can set the mood of the views and/or students allowing them to focus clearly on the video.	4.08	0.88	Manifested
4. Is not confusing and does not distract the viewers attention	4.15	0.79	Manifested
5. Makes the lessons easier to understand and more interesting.	4.55	0.68	Highly Manifested
Overall	4.30	0.51	Manifested

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Manifested; 3.50-4.49 Manifested; 2.50-3.49 Moderately Manifested; 1.50-2.49 Fairly Manifested; 1.00-1.49 Not Manifested

Table 6 shows that the perception of the students on the characteristics of video tutorials in terms of audio quality. The students find the audio quality highly manifested with two indicators, indicator 2 “it shows a clear and matches the order of the topics and learnings” with the highest mean of 4.58 followed by indicator 5 “the make the lessons easier to understand and more interesting” with the mean of 4.55. The indicator 3 “The sound can set the mood of the views and/or students allowing them to focus clearly on the video.” obtained the lowest mean of 4.08 with the verbal interpretation of manifested.

It has highlighted the several video benefits as an appealing educational tool that attracts the attention of the kids, including many multimedia elements (e.g., the mix of sound and visual movement), the ability of to supply it on time and place of students' choice, with the potential of repeating the skill indefinitely (Berk, 2009).

In addition to the video length, there were discovered some other characteristics that, according to other studies, should be considered to create an effective e-learning video, such as presenting the video along with the instructor's voiceover (Ou et al., 2019), showing the instructor face (Wang et al. 2020), and adding captions to the video (Jae, 2019). Therefore, sound can sets the learners interest in following the steps indicated on the video tutorial. The clear and good voice quality creates and maintain their interest to finish and follow the video.

Table 7 displays that the perception of the students on the characteristics of video tutorials in terms of visual quality. Indicator 2 obtained the highest mean of 4.38, “Provides attractive look that can capture the student's attention.” with manifested verbal interpretation, while indicator 4, “Patterns help us create a more accurate form.” has the lowest mean of 4.23 with the verbal interpretation manifested.

Table 7
Respondents' Perception on the Components of Video Tutorials in Teaching Bread and Pastry Production in terms of Objectives

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
<i>In video tutorials the objectives...</i>			
1. Provide a measurable and observable situation that match with the Training Regulations of TESDA	4.15	0.74	Manifested
2. Show the clear purpose of the lesson	4.40	0.84	Manifested
3. Describe how well the students will do.	4.53	0.66	Highly Manifested
4. Are achievable and include clear, transferable learning goals that give students greater control.	4.26	0.87	Manifested
5. Can suggest the outcomes in the affective, psychomotor, and cognitive domain	3.94	0.81	Manifested
Overall	4.25	0.55	Manifested

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Manifested; 3.50-4.49 Manifested; 2.50-3.49 Moderately Manifested; 1.50-2.49 Fairly Manifested; 1.00-1.49 Not Manifested

This supports that educational videos that emphasize these two aspects and include live examples will assist visual/auditory learning-style students in responding better, maintaining their attention, and improving their memory (Higgins et al., 2018).

The visual quality catch the students' interest and help them picture out the output that is expected to them. Hence, the visual presentation of the lesson has a great impact to capture the learners' attention. The more they can see new and unique method the more they are interested in the lesson.

Table 8
Respondents' Frequency of Use of the Video tutorial

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
<i>In video tutorial to fully understand and perform the task...</i>			
1. I repeatedly watch the given video to comprehensively absorb the lesson	3.69	0.76	Often
2. I pause the video from time to time to understand some segments or parts of the lesson.	3.92	1.08	Often
3. I take down important notes while watching video tutorials.	3.76	1.20	Often
4. I completely watch the video to understand the task.	4.17	1.05	Often
5. I prefer doing the task while the video is playing.	3.55	1.17	Often
Overall	3.82	0.65	Often

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Always; 3.50-4.49 Often; 2.50-3.49 Sometimes; 1.50-2.49 Seldom; 1.00-1.49 Never

Table 8 displays the student's frequency of use on the video tutorials. The indicator 4 "I completely watch the video to understand the task." obtained the highest mean of 4.17 with the verbal interpretation of Often followed by indicator 2 "I pause the video from time to time to understand some segments or parts of the lesson." obtained 3.92 mean with verbal interpretation of Often. While the lowest mean comes from indicator 5 "I prefer doing the task while the video is playing." obtained 3.55 mean with verbal interpretation Often.

The data implies that to be able to understand a task or a skill to be performed, most of them completely watched the video tutorial. While some repeatedly watch the video tutorial to finish the task. There are slow and fast learners but as educators we ensure that all of them can gain knowledge and skills in lesson.

Therefore, the learners repeatedly watched the video tutorials to perform the task. This supports the research by Takeda. Takeuchi and Haruna (2007) showed the ability to use video to motivate. Student learning, approaching educational principles, and lowering instructors' teaching responsibilities, particularly in mastering skills that require repeating movies more than once.

Part III. Students Baking Performance

Table 9 shows the level of students' baking performance in terms of Presentation. The table indicates that the rating 85-89 obtained the highest frequency of 51 or 65.39 percent with verbal interpretation "Very Good".

Table 9
Level of Student Baking Performance in terms of Presentation

Rating Scale	Frequency	Percentage	Verbal Interpretation
90-100	11	24.10	Excellent
85-89	51	65.39	Very Good
80-84	15	19.23	Good
75-79	1	1.28	Fair
74- & below	-	-	Poor
Total	78	100	

Legend: 90-100 Excellent; 85-89 Very Good; 80-84- Good; 75-79 Fair; 74 & below - Poor

It is followed by rating 80-84 with a frequency of 15 or 19.23 percent with verbal interpretation “Good”. Next, is the rating of 90-100 with a frequency of 11 or 24.10 percent with verbal interpretation “Excellent”. Lastly, the rating of 75-79 with a frequency of 1 or 1.28 percent with verbal interpretation “Fair”. As the table shows, most of the students rating is proficient with the use of online video tutorials. Presentation is a vital component of bakery items. It can make the baked product more appealing, aid in branding, and set it apart from competition. To produce unique and appealing patterns on bakery products, utilize decorating skills such as icing, fondant, edible printing, and piping.

Table 10
Level of Student Baking Performance in terms of Taste & Texture

Rating Scale	Frequency	Percentage	Verbal Interpretation
90-100	56	71.80	Excellent
85-89	21	26.92	Very Good
80-84	1	1.28	Good
75-79	-	-	Fair
74- & below	-	-	Poor
Total	78	100	

Legend: 90-100 Excellent; 85-89 Very Good; 80-84- Good; 75-79 Fair; 74 & below - Poor

Table 10 shows the level of students baking performance in terms of Taste and Texture. It indicates that the highest frequency of 56 or 71.80 percent has the rating of 90-100 with verbal interpretation “Excellent”. Followed by the rating of 85-89 with a frequency of 21 or 26.92 percent with verbal interpretation “Very Good”. The least frequency has the rating 80-84 obtained 1 or 1.28 percent with verbal interpretation “Good”. This implies that the majority of the students’ cake taste and texture is appealing after they watched the video tutorials.

Freshness perception is an important aspect in customer choice and acceptance of bakery items, which is linked to texture and other features. Lack of freshness in bakery and pastry goods reduces quality over time and is connected to how textural characteristics change. On the other hand, the mechanical qualities of foods rely on how food ingredients are blended and processed during manufacturing, which influences their texture as well as the stability that texture is (Silva et.al, 2017). According to Garcia-Gomez (2022), the key sensory features of bread are the dough’s resistance to deformations, the balance of elasticity and viscosity, and the pace of dough development (rising). Consumer acceptability of bread may be connected to its moisture content, which is therefore associated with freshness.

Table 11
Level of Student Baking Performance in terms of Time Management

Rating Scale	Frequency	Percentage	Verbal Interpretation
90-100	41	52.56	Excellent
85-89	37	47.44	Very Good
80-84	-	-	Good
75-79	-	-	Fair
74- & below	-	-	Poor
Total	78	100	

Legend: 90-100 Excellent; 85-89 Very Good; 80-84- Good; 75-79 Fair; 74 & below - Poor

Table 11 shows the level of students baking performance in terms of Time Management. The data reveals that the rating 90-100 has the highest frequency of 41 or 52.56 percent with verbal interpretation “Excellent”. Accordingly, the rating of 85-89 has a total of 37 frequency or 47.44 percent with verbal interpretation “Very Good”.

The result denotes that students completed the task in the time allotted. The time limit was strictly monitored due to the one hour time allotment only in the subject TLE, also for them not to be late to their next subject. Cleaning time is included in the time allotment to make sure they can follow and achieve other competencies aligned to this components of video tutorials.

They also recommended that businesses, as well as individuals, cultivate the habit of time management in order to succeed in their careers. The findings of Adebisi (2013), demonstrated that majority of the firms evaluated used time management to withstand competition and get more revenue.

Table 12
Level of Student Average Baking Performance

Rating Scale	Frequency	Percentage	Verbal Interpretation
90-100	18	23.08	Excellent
85-89	24	30.77	Very Good
80-84	20	25.64	Good
75-79	16	20.51	Fair
74- & below	-	-	Poor
Total	78	100	

Legend: 90-100-Excellent; 85-89- Very Good; 80-84- Good; 75-79- Fair; 74 & below - Poor

Table 12 is the level of the students’ baking performance using the video tutorials in terms of average baking performance. The rating of 85-89 obtained the highest frequency of 24 with a percentage of 30.77 and verbal interpretation of very good. The result implies most of the students is capable of their baking performance using video tutorials. It follows that the components, characteristics and frequency of using the video tutorials has an impact in the average baking performance. Most of them performed very well though some of them are first timers in terms of baking. The video tutorials and the students cognitive capabilities in learning a skill should be aligned and improve the skills and knowledge of the students.

Table 13
Significant relationship between student’s perception in video tutorials and their baking performance, in terms of technical skills.

Video Tutorials	Baking Performance Technical Skills			
	Presentation	Taste & Texture	Time Management	Average Performance
A. Components				
Objectives	0.058	0.146	-0.048	0.119
Content	0.097	0.172	-0.056	0.090
Instructions	0.056	0.166	-0.083	0.106
B. Characteristics				
Audio Quality	-0.016	0.098	-0.102	-0.045
Visual Quality	-0.053	0.012	0.096	-0.041
C. Frequency of Use				
	-0.0172	-0.041	0.008	-0.098

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 13 shows the result of the two-tailed Pearson correlation for the significant relationship between the components of video tutorials such as objectives, content, instructions, audio quality, visual quality and frequency of use in terms of Presentation, Taste and Texture, Time Management and Overall baking performance.

As for the Presentation result there is no correlation between all of the components of video tutorials ranging from -0.016 - 0.09. Meanwhile, there is a weak positive correlation between the Taste & Texture and the objectives, content, instructions of video tutorials presented ranging from 0.146 - 0.172 result. Furthermore, there is a weak negative correlation between Time Management and the audio quality with the result of -0.102. Moreover, the Overall performance has a weak positive correlation between the objectives and instruction with the result of 0.119 and 0.106 respectively.

On the other hand, the video tutorial component in terms of Objectives has a weak positive correlation between the taste & texture and average baking performance obtained a 0.146 and 0.119 result. In terms of Content, there is also a weak positive correlation between the taste and texture with the result of 0.172. Also in Instruction, there is a weak positive correlation between Taste & Texture and Overall with the result of 0.166 and 0.106.

Similarly with the characteristic of the video tutorial in terms of Audio quality there is a negative weak correlation between Taste and texture with -0.102 result. Nevertheless, both Visual Quality and Frequency of Use has no correlation with presentation, taste and texture, time management and overall student performance ranging from -0.041 to 0.096.

The data reveal that the video tutorials components, characteristics and frequency of use has no correlations to the baking performances of the students. According to Backberg et al. (2021) also measured video perceptions in order to generate best-practice guidelines. They found that there was motivation to engage in video-based learning since it allowed them to explore with many possibilities and helped them understand the relationship between parts and the whole. Slowing down and restarting in order to rewatch, observe, and take better notes helps to a more adaptive workplace.

The video tutorials can be used in gaining and mastering skills as well as developing the cognitive thinking skills. The presentation, taste and texture and time management criteria in their baking performance can be achieved by utilizing the video tutorials given or finding other videos related to the lessons. It is nowadays a need to include video tutorials as a learning tool to increase students understanding and as well as their performance.

Table 14
Significant relationship between video tutorials and the average baking performances of the respondents

Video Tutorial	Student's Average Baking Performance
Components	
Objectives	0.090
Content	0.155
Instructions	0.130
Characteristics	
Audio Quality	0.131
Visual Quality	0.247*
Frequency of Use	0.267*

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 14 reveals the significant relationship between video tutorials and students' average baking performance. The data show that there is no correlation in using video tutorials in terms of objectives with a 0.090 value. On the other hand, in terms of content of the video tutorials it has a weak positive correlation with a value of 0.155 and likewise with the instruction it also has a weak positive correlation with a value of 0.130.

Moreover, the result on the characteristic of video tutorials in terms of audio quality, reveals that there is a weak positive correlation with a 0.131 value. It was followed by the visual quality there is a weak positive correlation with a value of 0.247. In terms of frequency of use there is weak positive correlation with a value of 0.267. The data shows that there is no significant relationship between video tutorials and students' average baking performance.

In relation to this, as video tutorials are available some of the student fail on their baking performance because they only follow and repeat the video to acquire the skill but not understand the overall lesson. This maybe the reason of low baking performance using video tutorials. However, there is a weak correlation between the visual quality and frequency of use to the students baking performance. The visual presentation of the video tutorial has an impact because they can see the output that is expected of them and the step by step procedure are clearly explained with written captions on the video. The same with the frequency of use, repeatedly watched and finished the tutorials gain more tips and styles before the baking performance. On the other hand, audio quality does not affect the baking performance due to the students are more focus on following the steps through watching and reading the captions found in the video. They are more interested in what they see and do not missed a single second to capture all the procedure and forgot to listen in the tutorial. Therefore, video tutorials has no significant effect in the student's baking performance of the TLE Grade 10 students except for visual quality and frequency of use indicating significant and non-significant relationship between the variable under study.

Conclusions

The following are the salient findings of the study. Among the 78 student respondents of San Antonio National High School, majority are male with an average age of 16 years old with parent's whose educational background is mostly secondary education with mostly has mobile data connection and with an average income of below P10,000.

As the student perception on video tutorials, in terms of components, objectives, content and instructions was "manifested" by the

students.

On the student perception on video tutorials, in terms of characteristics, audio and visual quality the students perceived their skill as “manifested” after the use of video tutorial.

Likewise with the perception on the frequency of use of the video tutorials the students perceived their skill as “Often” after the use of video tutorial.

As for the student baking performance, it was revealed that the most of the students got “Very Good” with grades from 85-89.

As for the student’s average baking performance it is revealed that there is no significant relationship between video tutorials and the student performance, except for visual quality and frequency of use.

Based on the data, it is concluded that the use of video tutorials in teaching, including their components, characteristics, and frequency of usage, has no significant relationship with baking performance, in terms of technical skills including presentation, taste, and texture, time management, and food safety and cleanliness. As a result, the hypothesis is sustained.

Subsequently, it was discovered that video tutorials has no significant relationship with students' average baking performance, except for visual quality and frequency of use indicating significant and non-significant relationship between the variables under study, hence the hypothesis is partially accepted.

Based on the findings of the study and the conclusion drawn, the following are recommended.

The school administrator may provide assistance and teaching tactics that are appropriate for Grade 10 learners for them to acquire the necessary baking skills in preparation for their senior high or collegiate level, as well as the essential training for instructors to increase their teaching ability.

Teachers of T.L.E. disciplines may explore using video tutorials as an educational tool to teach TLE subjects and improve students' baking abilities and performance. This is because the students perceived it to be important for them to learn baking skills. It will also assist the teacher in improving and developing their teaching strategies.

This study also suggests alternative approaches and strategies for educating the Grade 10 baking learners. Improvement of the school facilities particularly the laboratories and availability of tools and equipment that can be used in their performance task. This may improve their cognitive as well as their baking skills in TLE.

Partnerships between educational institutions, local governments, and relevant stakeholders is vital for creating supportive settings that encourage interactive learning and secure a livelihood for the students and their households.

These studies may be carried out by future researchers to keep in touch with the new teaching methods using video tutorials to gain baking skills and to improve their competence in this field.

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